

SND Strategic Plan 2023–2026

Vision and Objectives

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Swedish National Data Service

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Introduction

The purpose of Swedish National Data Service (SND) is to provide a coordinated and secure structure for describing, depositing, sharing, and finding research data. SND is governed by a consortium consisting of nine universities: University of Gothenburg, Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University. From 2023 to 2026 SND will continue to develop and expand its activities. The organization will support a network that includes nearly all Swedish HEIs, in addition to several other research institutes, in establishing and running local data access units (DAUs). By the end of the period, these efforts will have had a crucial impact on researchers' and universities' ability to achieve the Swedish government's objective of open access to research information by 2026.

According to the Swedish Research Council's funding agreement, the purpose of the SND infrastructure is:

1. To facilitate the sharing of research data in a simple, secure and reliable way, which at the same time meets the requirements for preservation, access and sharing.
2. To make data visible and offer user statistics by presenting research data nationally and internationally and providing information on how data is shared and cited.
3. To facilitate reliable access to searchable, high-quality, and well-documented research data, together with information on how this data can be accessed and reused.

The focus of *SND Strategic Plan 2023–2026* is to declare our vision and describe the strategic objectives of the national research infrastructure. The strategic plan consists of two parts:

- The vision with a short description of the mission and the overall purpose of the infrastructure
- The three overarching strategic areas with specific objectives:
 - Knowledge hub
 - Networks and collaborations
 - Tools and services

In addition to the strategic plan, SND will present annual operational plans, important priorities for the coming year, time schedules and specified action points for each objective.

Vision

Our vision is to be a leading actor in a global network through which researchers can easily share, find, access, and reuse high-quality research data – now and in the future.

We will make this happen by inspiring, supporting, and coordinating the development of a trustworthy system of research data repositories in Sweden.

Knowledge hub

Objectives:

- To maintain and expand expertise
Comment: The SND office and domain specialists will initiate and participate in activities aimed at maintaining, widening, and deepening relevant expertise in and know-how /about/ metadata requirements, means of access, new technologies, and how to manage and preserve new data types.
- To disseminate knowledge and provide training
Comment: The SND office and domain specialists will coordinate the sharing of expertise within its various networks, and among researchers and data professionals.
- To acquire knowledge
Comment: The SND office and domain specialists will initiate and participate in activities that aim to acquire and contribute with new knowledge regarding data curation, management, and preservation.

Networks and collaborations

Objectives:

- To expand and maintain SND's networks
Comment: SND will coordinate and extend the DAU network and establish new networks of professions and infrastructures for the purpose of fostering knowledge exchange.
- To support the DAU network institutions in being certified as Trusted Digital Repositories.
Comment: SND will continue to encourage and offer support to network institutions in their attempts to become certified.
- To coordinate and support distributed expertise
Comment: SND will coordinate and support Domain Expert activities and Open Data Flagships.
- To maintain and expand national and international collaborations
Comment: SND will maintain and expand its collaborations and connections to other relevant research data infrastructures, e-infrastructures, and public authorities.

Tools & Services

Objectives:

- To develop and maintain a national research data portal
Comment: SND will facilitate access to searchable, high-quality, and well-documented research data. This will be achieved by providing a national research data portal in cooperation with relevant stakeholders.

- To provide metadata management tools & systems
Comment: SND will continue to provide high-quality, user-friendly, FAIR-compliant data documentation tools and services that allow description and management of high-quality data.

- To provide the SND CARE systems & services
Comment: SND will continue to develop its TDR certified repository service (SND CARE) for researchers from institutions that do not provide storage that complies with technical requirements of the SND research data portal.

- To be the CESSDA ERIC National Service Provider
Comment: SND will continue to be an active Service Provider for CESSDA ERIC and contribute to its projects and events.